

ERMAKOV EQUATIONS IN QUANTUM MECHANICS

ROUMEN TSEKOV

Department of Physical Chemistry, University of Sofia, 1 James Bourchiers Blvd., 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria

Abstract. The Ermakov equation, appearing in quantum mechanics of a harmonic oscillator, is extended via dissipative and thermal terms to take into account the effect of an environment.

More than a century ago Ermakov [1] has introduced an equation, which appears in many branches of modern physics [2, 3]. In quantum mechanics the Ermakov equation comes out in the case of a harmonic oscillator [4, 5]. The evolution of the latter is usually described by the time-dependent Schrödinger equation

$$i\hbar\partial_t\psi = (-\hbar^2\partial_x^2 / 2m + m\omega_0^2x^2 / 2)\psi \quad (1)$$

where m is the particle mass and ω_0 is the oscillator own frequency. The complex wave function $\psi(x, t)$ can be presented generally in the polar form

$$\psi = \sqrt{\rho} \exp(iS / \hbar) \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the probability density and S is the wave function phase. Introducing Eq. (2) in Eq. (1) the latter splits in two equations [6]

$$\partial_t\rho = -\partial_x(\rho V) \quad (3)$$

$$m\partial_t V + mV\partial_x V + m\omega_0^2x = -\partial_x Q \quad (4)$$

corresponding to the imaginary and real parts. The first equation is a continuity one and $V \equiv \partial_x S / m$ is the hydrodynamic-like velocity in the probability space.

Equation (4) is a macroscopic force balance, where $Q = -\hbar^2 \partial_x^2 \sqrt{\rho} / 2m\sqrt{\rho}$ is the Bohm quantum potential. The solution of these Madelung equations

$\rho = \exp(-x^2 / 2\sigma^2) / \sqrt{2\pi}\sigma$ is a Gaussian probability density, which introduced in Eq. (3) leads to an expression $V = x\dot{\sigma} / \sigma$ for the hydrodynamic-like velocity. Substituting now both expressions for ρ and V in Eq. (4) results in the Ermakov equation describing the evolution of the rms displacement σ

$$m\ddot{\sigma} + m\omega_0^2\sigma = \hbar^2 / 4m\sigma^3 \quad (5)$$

Pinney [7] has found a general solution of the Ermakov equation. In the case of a free quantum particle ($\omega_0 = 0$) the solution of Eq. (5) is the well-known expression, describing ballistic spreading of a Gaussian wave packet, $\sigma^2 = \sigma_0^2 + (\hbar t / 2m\sigma_0)^2$

The Madelung presentation of the Schrödinger equation opens a door for introduction of dissipative forces in quantum mechanics. Usually the friction force of a particle in a classical environment depends linearly on the particle velocity. Hence, one can add a friction force $-bV$ in Eq. (4) to obtain [8, 9]

$$m\partial_t V + mV\partial_x V + bV + m\omega_0^2 x = -\partial_x Q \quad (6)$$

where b is the particle friction coefficient. Thus one arrives to dissipative Madelung hydrodynamics. Substituting the expressions for ρ and V in Eq. (6) yields a dissipative Ermakov equation [8-10, 3]

$$m\ddot{\sigma} + b\dot{\sigma} + m\omega_0^2\sigma = \hbar^2 / 4m\sigma^3 \quad (7)$$

In the case of a strong friction one can neglect the first inertial term in Eq. (7) and

the solution of the remaining equation is $\sigma^2 = (\hbar / 2m\omega_0) \sqrt{1 - \exp(-4m\omega_0^2 t / b)}$ [11]. It describes the relaxation of an initially excited oscillator to the ground state.

In the case of a free dissipative quantum particle ($\omega_0 = 0$) this solution reduces to a known sub-diffusive law $\sigma^2 = \hbar \sqrt{t / mb}$ [11].

Equation (7) describes a dissipative quantum oscillator at zero temperature. In the case of a finite temperature the following thermal dissipative Ermakov equation is obtained [9]

$$m\ddot{\sigma} + b\dot{\sigma} + m\omega_0^2\sigma = 2\partial_\beta(1/\sigma)_b + \hbar^2 / 4m\sigma^3 \quad (8)$$

where $\beta = 1/k_b T$ and the subscript $_b$ indicates that the differentiation on β is carried out at constant friction coefficient. This equation reduces to Eq. (7) at $T \rightarrow 0$ and its equilibrium solution $\sigma_\infty^2 = (\hbar / 2m\omega_0) \coth(\beta\hbar\omega_0 / 2)$ corresponds to the well-known expression from the quantum statistical thermodynamics. However, in the classical limit Eq. (8) differs from a well-known result. In the case of thermo-quantum diffusion Eq. (6) can be generalized to [12]

$$m\partial_t V + mV\partial_x V + bV + m\omega_0^2 x = -\partial_x (\ln \rho + \int_0^\beta Q d\beta)_b / \beta \quad (9)$$

Substituting here the expressions for ρ and V yields another Ermakov-like equation which provides the correct classical limit

$$m\ddot{\sigma} + b\dot{\sigma} + m\omega_0^2\sigma = [1/\sigma + \sigma \int_0^\beta (\hbar^2 / 4m\sigma^4)_b d\beta] / \beta \quad (10)$$

The equilibrium solution of Eq. (10) is again $\sigma_\infty^2 = (\hbar / 2m\omega_0) \coth(\beta\hbar\omega_0 / 2)$. In the high temperature limit both equations (8) and (10) reduces to

$$m\ddot{\sigma} + b\dot{\sigma} + m\omega_0^2\sigma = k_b T / \sigma + \hbar^2 / 4m\sigma^3 \quad (11)$$

The equilibrium solution of Eq. (11) $\sigma_\infty^2 = [\sqrt{1 + (\beta\hbar\omega_0)^2} + 1] / 2\beta m\omega_0^2$ provides the correct limits at low and high temperatures. This thermal dissipative Ermakov equation is solved in the case of strong friction, where the first inertial term is neglected [13].

Finally, the Ermakov equation allows exploring other dissipative models in quantum mechanics. For instance, one can add in Eq. (5) a jerk term, heuristically corresponding to the Abraham-Lorentz force [14], to obtain

$$m\ddot{\sigma} - r\ddot{\ddot{\sigma}} + m\omega_0^2\sigma = \hbar^2 / 4m\sigma^3 \quad (12)$$

where $r = e^2 / 6\pi\epsilon_0 c^3$, e is the particle charge and c is the speed of light. Thus, Eq. (12) describes a charged quantum harmonic oscillator dissipating energy via electromagnetic radiation.

REFERENCES

1. Ermakov, V. P. *Univ. Izv. (Kiev)*, **20**, 1880, 1.
2. Leach, P.G.L. and K. Andriopoulos. *Appl. Anal. Discrete Math.*, **2** 2008, 146.
3. Haas, F. *Phys. Scr.*, **81**, 2010 025004.
4. Nassar, A. B. *Phys. Rev.*, **32**, 1985, 1986 *Phys. Rev.*, **33** 1986, 4433.
5. Schuch, D. *SIGMA*, **4**, 2008, 043.
6. Madelung, E. *Z. Phys.*, **40**, 1927, 322.
7. Pinney, E. *Proc. Am. Math. Soc.*, **1**, 1950, 681.
8. Nassar, A. B. *J. Phys. A: Math. Gen.*, **18**, 1985, L509.
9. Tsekov, R. and G.N. Vayssilov. *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, **195**, 1992, 423.
10. Nassar, A. B. *J. Math. Phys.*, **27**, 1986, 755.
11. Tsekov, R. *Int. J. Theor. Phys.*, **48**, 2009, 630.
12. Tsekov, R. *Int. J. Theor. Phys.*, **48**, 2009, 85.
13. Messer, J.A. *GEB Univ. Giessen*, 2008, 6328.
14. Abraham, M. *Theorie der Elektrizität* (Leipzig: Teubner), 1905.

Received on March 19, 2010